

The Psychological and Economic Dynamics of Migrant Workers: Effects of Low Wages, Unemployment, and Integration in Enterprises

*To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 6-07,
2024, p. 10– 38 - 0099-0001-2407-0102.*

*Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by
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Georgia")*

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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challenges such as working in low-paying jobs and dealing with the risk of unemployment. This article examines the psychological and economic dynamics of migrant workers, particularly focusing on the effects of factors such as low wages, unemployment, and integration in businesses.

ABSTRACT

While migrant workers constitute a significant portion of the global labor market, they often face

The effects of low wages on the psychological health of migrant workers are a significant concern. Low wages can affect workers' living standards, leading to psychological issues such as stress, anxiety, and

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depression. This situation can diminish the motivation of migrant workers employed in businesses and reduce productivity.

Unemployment can make it difficult for migrant workers to cope with feelings of economic insecurity. Along with income loss and the risk of social exclusion, unemployment exacerbates uncertainties during the job search process. This can negatively impact the mental well-being of migrant workers and diminish their motivation to seek employment.

Integration refers to the process through which migrant workers adapt socially and culturally to a new environment. Integration policies and practices in businesses can strengthen the social support and connections of migrant workers in the workplace. Encouraging multicultural work environments in

businesses can enhance the psychological well-being of migrant workers.

In conclusion, it is important for businesses to consider factors such as low wages, unemployment, and integration to improve the psychological and economic well-being of migrant workers. This is a crucial step for both the sustainability of businesses and the quality of life of migrant workers. This article aims to contribute to understanding the experiences of migrant workers within businesses by thoroughly examining these issues.

Keywords: Migrant Workers, Low Wages, Unemployment, Integration, Psychological Health, Economic Well-Being, Business, Multicultural Work Environment, Social Support, Motivation.

INTRODUCTION

In this article, the focus will be on understanding the psychological and economic dynamics of migrant workers in businesses. Migrant workers play a significant role in the global labor market, often facing challenges such as working in low-wage jobs and unemployment. Moreover, the process of integrating into a new cultural and social environment poses a significant challenge for these workers. In this context, the role of businesses is crucial in understanding and improving the psychological and economic well-being of migrant workers.

The article aims to explore the impact of psychological and economic factors on migrant workers' experiences in businesses. Specifically, it will examine how factors such as low wages, unemployment, and integration affect the psychological health and economic welfare of migrant workers. Additionally, the importance of businesses in fostering multicultural work environments and providing social support to migrant workers will also be discussed.

Migrant workers often experience psychological issues primarily stemming from economic hardships such as low wages and unemployment. Low wages can impact their living standards and lead to stress, anxiety, and depression. Similarly, unemployment brings uncertainties in job search, income loss, and risks of social exclusion, all contributing to psychological distress. Therefore, it is critical for businesses to adopt effective policies to enhance the economic welfare of migrant workers.

Integration is also a significant factor influencing the psychological and economic well-being of migrant workers. Adapting to a new cultural and social environment poses a significant challenge for migrant workers employed in businesses. However, businesses

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can facilitate this process and support migrant workers by implementing integration policies and practices, thereby aiding their productivity and well-being in the workplace.

This article aims to fill the knowledge gap by exploring measures that businesses can take to understand and improve the experiences of migrant workers within their organizations. Enhancing the psychological and economic well-being of migrant workers is not only crucial for business sustainability but also for societal welfare as a whole.

AIM

Understanding the psychological and economic dynamics of migrant workers is crucial in today's global economy and societal structure. This research aims to examine the psychological and economic impacts of prominent issues such as low wages, unemployment, and integration among migrant workers in businesses. Specifically, the goal is to deeply understand how economic challenges like low wages and unemployment affect the psychological health and social integration of migrant workers.

This study aims to investigate the challenges faced by migrant workers and their implications at the organizational level, aiming to inform policymakers, business owners, and the broader society. Additionally, examining the barriers and support mechanisms encountered by migrant workers in their economic integration process will shed light on future policy and business strategies.

The findings of this research will significantly contribute to understanding migrant workers' experiences within businesses, thereby facilitating the development of more inclusive policies and business practices. Ultimately, this study aims to contribute to better addressing the economic and psychological needs of migrant workers and to foster the development of fairer and more sustainable business models.

METHOD

This study will conduct a literature review to examine the psychological and economic dynamics of migrant workers in relation to the effects of low wages, unemployment, and integration within businesses. The literature review will compile existing knowledge by reviewing scholarly works that explore the experiences and impacts of migrant workers on these issues. This review will encompass both qualitative and quantitative research and synthesize information from various disciplines.

The literature review will be conducted using a variety of sources such as published academic articles, book chapters, doctoral theses, and international reports. It aims to cover literature that helps us understand the psychological and economic dynamics of

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migrant workers in the context of low wages, unemployment, and integration within businesses.

The process of literature review will involve comprehensive searches conducted in online academic databases, as well as in libraries and other repositories. Keywords and subject headings will be utilized to identify relevant studies.

The collected literature will be systematically examined to identify key findings and trends. The findings will highlight the current state of research on the psychological and economic dynamics of migrant workers and identify gaps in knowledge.

The results of the literature review will contribute to understanding the psychological and economic dynamics of migrant workers and will provide a foundation for further research.

RESULTS

A. Migration: Conceptual Framework

Migration is a demographic phenomenon encompassing the movement of people for various reasons; this concept includes the movements of refugees, displaced persons, stateless individuals, and economic migrants (Glossary on Migration Terms, 2009). According to the World Bank, the term migrant refers to a person who leaves their country of residence for any reason. Many countries define migrants as individuals born in another country (World Bank, 2017).

Migration is a term that cannot be definitively defined due to its varied transformations throughout human history and its dynamic nature. This is because subjective definitions are influential. Sociologically, developing a common and holistic definition of migration poses significant challenges; each migration flow has its unique reasons and forms of occurrence (Güneş, 2012:185). In the literature, the concept of migration has been defined within the frameworks of different scientific disciplines rather than specific definitions.

Migration generally occurs due to social, political, economic, and natural reasons (Şen, 2014; Ekici and Tuncel, 2015; Başel, 2007; Yılmaz, 2014). According to Şimşek and Koçancı (2018:166), reasons for migration include desire for family reunification, improving living standards, climate conditions, educational opportunities, and personal security.

Escapes triggered by factors such as political persecution, civil war, famine, environmental disasters, and political pressures are included in the general category of migration (Rystad, 1992:1168). For example, the forced, irregular, and mass migration movement from Syria to Turkey is a significant example in this context. The main

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reason for this migration movement is the deterioration of security conditions, as mentioned above.

Trends in migration studies emphasize that relying on a single discipline or analytical method is insufficient for fully understanding the modern phenomenon of migration. Migration is a complex phenomenon that requires a sophisticated theory encompassing its various aspects, different perspectives, levels, and assumptions (Massey et al., 1993: 432). Therefore, identifying commonalities among migration theories from different disciplines is necessary to develop a unified migration theory (Gezgin, 1991: 34).

Migration theories are generally categorized into two main types: traditional and modern. In the context of our interest, one significant modern migration theory is Network Theory. According to this theory, migrant networks constitute interpersonal relationships that connect migrants and potential migrants through kinship, friendship, and shared community ties. These networks enhance international mobility opportunities by reducing the costs and risks associated with migration, thereby increasing migrants' net gains (Massey et al., 1993: 448). Through these networks, it is expected that individuals who have previously migrated will transmit their experiences of challenges to potential migrants. The network of relationships facilitates issues such as finding employment, housing, and sustaining living conditions between migrants and potential migrants. Therefore, this theory also plays a crucial role in the socio-economic integration of migrants with the host community.

Migration types can vary based on causes, consequences, durations, regional changes, and migrant density. For instance, the migration movement from Syria to Turkey is classified as forced, mass, and irregular migration. Turkey has been the most affected country by this migration flow. The proximity of Syria to Turkey and Turkey's open-door policy have influenced this situation. As of May 9, 2024, Turkey hosts approximately 3,057,762 Syrian migrants, which constitutes about 3.5% of Turkey's population (Turkey's population was approximately 85,372,377 as of December 31, 2023). According to the United Nations, the term migrant encompasses anyone residing in a foreign country for more than one year, with migration status being both voluntary and involuntary. The concepts of refugee and asylum seeker are used when individuals or communities relocate due to compulsory reasons. Under the 1951 Geneva Convention, Turkey uses the refugee concept for migrants coming from European countries, but considering that Syrian migrants left their country due to compulsory reasons, it would be more appropriate to consider them under migrant or refugee status. Syrian migrants in Turkey are governed by the Temporary Protection Regulation of the Law on Foreigners and International Protection. This regulation temporarily protects individuals or groups who have migrated compulsorily either individually or collectively.

B. The Psychological Health Status, Stress Factors, Adaptation Processes, and Psychological Effects of Workplace Experiences of Immigrant Workers

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According to the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), as of mid-2021, there were 84 million forcibly displaced people worldwide, with 26 million of them classified as refugees. Turkey, according to UNHCR's official data, hosts the largest number of refugees globally, accommodating 3.7 million refugees.

Based on these estimates, Turkey is known to host approximately 3.7 million registered refugees, with an additional estimated 5 million undocumented migrants, bringing the total to around 5 million. The increasing number of refugees worldwide also increases the demand for labor in this field. Among professionals working with refugees are psychologists, doctors, translators, lawyers, social workers, psychiatrists, and counselors. Studies in the literature indicate that these professionals often experience various psychological challenges such as Secondary Trauma (ST), Vicarious Trauma (VT), anxiety, depression, sleep disorders, and burnout when working with refugees (Borho et al., 2019; Kindermann et al., 2017; Zivanovic & Markovic, 2020).

The World Health Organization defines psychological health as a state where individuals are aware of their own abilities, can manage normal stresses of life, and can contribute productively to society. It is well recognized that working with refugees can have adverse effects on psychologists and other health professionals due to frequently encountering traumatic experiences.

Trauma refers to any distressing life event that adversely affects a person's psychological and physical integrity. However, not every stressful event in daily life qualifies as trauma.

Traumatic events are serious incidents that individuals find overwhelming and lead to long-term psychological difficulties (Briere & Scott, 2014). These can include large-scale events such as natural disasters, wars, human-made disasters, as well as smaller-scale incidents like motor vehicle accidents, sexual assault, domestic violence (Ehlers & Clark, 2003; Forneris et al., 2013). It is important to understand the concept of trauma before evaluating Secondary Trauma (ST) and Vicarious Trauma (VT).

The American Psychiatric Association's Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5) defines a traumatic event as "experiencing, witnessing, or being confronted with an event or events that involve actual or threatened death or serious injury, or a threat to the physical integrity of oneself or others" (DSM-5, p. 265).

Following traumatic experiences, individuals may develop reactions such as Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) (Forneris et al., 2013). Individuals with PTSD may involuntarily relive the traumatic event through recurring memories (flashbacks) or nightmares. This condition can lead to persistent negative emotional states, feelings of detachment from others, and a sense of alienation (APA, 2013).

Secondary Trauma (ST) refers to the psychological impact experienced by an individual as a result of exposure to others' traumatic experiences. Vicarious Trauma (VT), on the other hand, involves the emotional toll experienced by an individual due to exposure to

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others' traumatic stories. These terms are commonly used to explain the risks professionals in trauma-related fields such as psychologists, social workers face when listening to and supporting individuals with traumatic experiences in their professional capacities.

The effects of a traumatic event are not necessarily contingent on directly experiencing the event oneself; witnessing another person's traumatic experience can also lead to traumatic effects (Figley, 1995). This phenomenon is commonly referred to in the literature as Secondary Trauma (ST) and Vicarious Trauma (VT).

Secondary trauma (ST) occurs when an individual witnesses another person's traumatic experience (Bride et al., 2004). In such cases, the person may experience symptoms similar to Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), such as intrusive thoughts, avoidance, and hyperarousal.

Vicarious trauma (VT), on the other hand, refers to the cumulative effects of working with traumatized individuals (Branson, 2019). According to Possick et al. (2015), vicarious trauma in therapy reflects the impact of a traumatized individual recounting details of their traumatic experience to the therapist. Similar to secondary trauma, vicarious trauma may manifest in symptoms akin to PTSD, including intrusive thoughts, avoidance behaviors, and a negative worldview (Aparicio et al., 2013).

McCann and Pearlman (1990) propose that therapists working with traumatized individuals may integrate their clients' memories into their own autobiographical narratives, potentially altering the therapist's self-perception. This process could lead to vicarious trauma for the therapist, crossing professional boundaries and possibly resulting in avoidance of discussing traumatic events (Iqbal, 2015).

Therefore, it is important for professionals working with traumatized individuals to seek appropriate support and supervision to protect themselves and maintain their health.

Studies in the literature compare the psychological effects of interpersonal trauma (one person mistreating another) with natural disasters (such as earthquakes, fires) and generally indicate that interpersonal trauma can lead to more devastating consequences (Berger, 2015; Kumar & Fonagy, 2013; Merrell, 2013).

Refugees are typically individuals who have left their countries due to life-threatening events such as war, violence, genocide, or torture, either experiencing these traumatic events themselves or witnessing them (Çırakoğlu & Kahil, 2018). In this context, professionals working with refugees (such as translators, social workers, psychologists, doctors) inevitably face serious traumatic experiences.

Among refugee workers, alongside Secondary Trauma (ST) and Vicarious Trauma (VT), psychological issues like depression, anxiety, and burnout are commonly observed. Depression is characterized as major depressive disorder, with symptoms

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including persistent sadness, loss of interest (anhedonia), difficulty concentrating, changes in sleep and appetite, loss of energy, psychomotor retardation, feelings of guilt, and thoughts of suicide (APA, 2013).

Anxiety, on the other hand, is defined as excessive worry and distress, with symptoms including shortness of breath, nausea, palpitations, and other somatic symptoms (Metin, 2010).

Burnout is a widespread problem resulting from unmanaged workplace stress. It encompasses dimensions such as emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and perceived decreased personal accomplishment (Foo et al., 2021). Burnout can lead to serious issues in work life and is commonly associated with other psychological problems (Jachens et al., 2018; Manning & Preston, 2003).

Therefore, it is critically important for professionals working with refugees to be trained to recognize and manage these psychological challenges effectively, and to seek support when needed.

Research indicates that professionals working with refugees, such as translators, psychologists, lawyers, social workers, and doctors, are prone to developing Secondary Trauma (ST) and Vicarious Trauma (VT).

For instance, according to a study by UNHCR, 38% of personnel working with refugees exhibit symptoms of ST (UNHCR Staff Well-being and Mental Health, 2016). Another study by Denkinger et al. (2018) found that 22.9% of social workers, psychologists, and translators working with refugees showed symptoms of ST, with 8.6% of these symptoms being severe.

Similarly, Espinosa et al. (2019) reported that 31.7% of professionals working with refugees displayed symptoms of ST.

One specific study focusing on lawyers working with refugees is that of Harris and Mellinger (2021). Their research revealed an average score of 2.95 on the ST scale among participating lawyers, which significantly exceeded the established cutoff point.

Regarding translators, Kindermann et al. (2020) conducted a study indicating that 21% of translators working with refugees exhibited symptoms of ST.

These studies underscore the significant risk of ST and VT among professionals working with refugees, highlighting the importance of support systems and interventions to mitigate these psychological challenges.

Studies emphasize that being a refugee poses a risk factor for translators themselves. For example, Denkinger et al. (2018), Miller et al. (2005), and Engstrom et al. (2010) have shown in their research that having a traumatic history increases the risk of developing Secondary Trauma (ST) among translators.

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These studies underscore that professionals working with refugees frequently encounter traumatic experiences and may be at risk of developing ST and Vicarious Trauma (VT) while coping with the effects of these experiences. Therefore, the education, support, and access to appropriate healthcare services tailored to the needs of these professional groups are crucial.

The variety and findings of studies assessing the frequency of Secondary Trauma (ST) and Vicarious Trauma (VT) among professionals working with refugees are quite striking.

A meta-analysis conducted by Roberts et al. (2021) revealed that the prevalence of ST among professionals working with refugees is approximately 45%. This finding underscores how widespread the effects of traumatic experiences encountered by professionals working with refugees are.

Rizkalla and Segal's (2019) research conducted in Jordan demonstrated that refugee workers are not only at risk for psychological health issues but also for physical health risks. This study found that Secondary Trauma (ST) is associated with negative physical health outcomes and high levels of physical pain among refugee workers. Additionally, it noted that refugee workers' identification with the refugees they assist (i.e., not seeing themselves as separate individuals) could have negative effects on their personal relationships and well-being.

Mishori et al.'s (2014) study on doctors working in assessment fields is also noteworthy. This study indicated that 26.2% of participants experienced Vicarious Trauma (VT). These findings underscore the importance of recognizing the potential for vicarious trauma among healthcare professionals working with refugees.

Studies in the literature on ST and VT often link having a traumatic history and certain demographic factors (e.g., gender) to the risk of developing ST (Denkinger et al., 2018; Acar, 2021). However, Hensel et al.'s (2015) meta-analysis revealed that the relationship between having a traumatic experience and demographic factors with developing ST is more complex than previously thought. In their study, they found that workload ratio (the proportion of working with individuals with traumatic experiences) was the strongest factor associated with ST.

Turgut's (2014) master's thesis in Turkey investigated the frequency of traumatic symptoms among professionals working with refugees, finding re-experiencing, avoidance, emotional numbing, and hyperarousal symptoms to be 28.9%, 15.6%, and 18.5%, respectively.

As a result, it emphasizes that professionals working with refugees are at high risk of developing trauma-related symptoms such as Secondary Trauma (ST) and Vicarious Trauma (VT), highlighting the need for support to maintain their health and

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functionality. In this context, further research and the development of effective support mechanisms for these professionals are crucial.

Studies on professionals working with Syrian refugees reveal the impact of traumatic experiences they encounter.

Ünal et al. (2017) found that 52.4% of professionals working with Syrian refugees were significantly preoccupied with the minds of those they assisted, indicating intense experiences of the effects of the trauma their clients experience.

Acar's (2021) study on professionals working with refugee and asylum seeker individuals in various cities in Turkey suggested that increased symptoms of secondary traumatic stress may exacerbate difficulties in emotional exhaustion and depersonalization components, potentially reducing perceived personal achievement levels. These findings indicate that refugee professionals are in a challenging work environment both emotionally and physically, which could negatively impact their long-term health and functionality.

Brooks and colleagues' (2022) study conducted in Istanbul focused on 104 refugee professionals working with Syrian refugees, revealing that 27.88% of participants exhibited symptoms of Secondary Trauma (ST). This finding underscores that refugee professionals in Turkey are under significant burden in terms of ST symptoms.

The studies mentioned above indicate that ST and VT frequencies are high among refugee professionals in different regions, generally yielding similar results. Therefore, it is crucial to implement supportive and protective measures for professionals working with refugees, improve working conditions, and enhance access to psychological health services.

1. Depression and Anxiety

Studies on professionals working with refugees clearly demonstrate the psychological challenges and impacts of trauma frequently encountered by these occupational groups. In this context, some of the studies include:

UNHCR Staff Well-being and Mental Health (2016) Report: This study, conducted with 2431 refugee workers, indicated prevalence rates of anxiety and depression at 31% and 25%, respectively, among the staff. These figures highlight that refugee workers contend significantly with psychological health issues.

- **Study by Ager et al. (2012):** This study, conducted with 376 individuals, reported a prevalence of 68% for depression and 53% for anxiety. These results indicate that refugee workers experience high levels of psychological stress, which can lead to various health problems.

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- **Study by Zivanovic and Markovic (2020):** This study, conducted with 270 refugee workers, revealed a prevalence of 20% for depression and 22.6% for anxiety among participants. These results indicate that refugee workers in different regions face similar challenges.
- **Study by Eriksson et al. (2013):** This study, conducted with 299 refugee workers, found a prevalence of 50.4% for anxiety and 55.2% for depression among participants. The study also examined risk factors contributing to the development of anxiety and depression, including the number of traumatic experiences, duration of work, and gender.
- **Lusk and Terrazas' study (2015):** This study conducted with participants working with Mexican refugees revealed that 83.8% of participants experienced sleep problems. Sleep issues emerge as one of the challenges faced by professionals working with refugees.

The common point of these studies is to demonstrate that refugee workers are under intense psychological stress, which negatively impacts their physical and mental health. Therefore, providing supportive work environments, regular psychological support, and managing workloads are essential requirements for these professionals.

Research aiming to examine the frequency of depression and anxiety among refugee workers highlights that these challenges, such as Secondary Trauma (ST) and Vicarious Trauma (VT), are quite prevalent.

2. Burnout

According to the BMMYK Psychological Health and Psychosocial Support report (2013), the three most common stress factors among employees are workload, feeling undervalued, and job tenure (contract status). Economic concerns also emerge as a significant stressor, given the uncertainty in job security for refugees who often engage in short-term projects. Eriksson et al.'s study (2013), conducted with 299 refugee workers, identified economic problems as the most prevalent stressor among participants (93.7%).

A study in Uganda involving 376 refugee workers found emotional exhaustion (45%), decreased personal accomplishment (24%), and depersonalization (30%) symptoms to be frequent (Ager et al., 2012). Another study with refugee workers in Greece reported a burnout prevalence of 57% among 217 participants (Chatzea et al., 2018). Research involving North Korean refugees indicated a burnout prevalence of 51.3% among 179 participants (Kim, 2017).

According to Roberts et al.'s meta-analysis (2021), the overall prevalence of burnout is approximately 32.1%. In a study conducted with Syrian refugees in Kilis, Turkey,

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emotional exhaustion (40%), depersonalization (19.6%), and decreased personal accomplishment (11.1%) were reported among 199 participants (Sağaltıcı, 2022).

In a study conducted by BMMYK with 2431 participants, emotional exhaustion (31%) and depersonalization (9%) frequencies were observed among participants (BMMYK, 2016). The same report indicated a decrease in perceived personal accomplishment at 43% and a secondary trauma (ST) prevalence of 38%. These findings underscore the significance of workplace stress and psychological challenges.

Eriksson et al. (2013) also examined risk factors for burnout. They found that holding a managerial position increased the risk of burnout by 5.2 times, while having experienced a traumatic event increased the risk by 5.1 times. However, having a supportive work team was identified as a protective factor against burnout.

The results from these studies highlight the widespread prevalence of burnout among refugee workers. Some studies indicating higher burnout rates compared to secondary trauma frequencies emphasize the importance of workplace challenges alongside other psychological health issues such as ST, DT, anxiety, depression, and sleep disorders. Literature findings clearly demonstrate the vulnerability of refugee workers to psychological problems, which could potentially impact service quality negatively.

The consequences of Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS) and Vicarious Trauma (VT), such as sleep problems, attention difficulties, dysfunctional coping methods, low motivation, and difficulty maintaining boundaries, have been well-documented (Figley, 1995). Additionally, a correlation has been found between STS symptoms and becoming overly detached from clients (Harrison & Westwood, 2009). Iqbal (2015) emphasized that VT can lead to unethical behaviors, such as avoiding discussions about a client's trauma. Killian (2008) noted that therapists working with traumatized individuals often experience distractibility and sleep issues.

In addition to decreasing service quality, the psychological challenges faced by refugee workers can lead to turnover and consequently loss of workforce. Bride (2007) identified STS and VT as major factors contributing to humanitarian aid workers leaving their jobs. Working with traumatized individuals requires time and experience to specialize in this field. Therefore, it is crucial for experienced professionals to continue working and mentor newcomers, as turnover among these individuals poses potential challenges to service quality and sustainability (Ebren et al., 2022).

Hensel et al.'s (2015) meta-analysis highlighted workload as a risk factor for STS, suggesting that organizations can enhance employees' psychological health by improving their working conditions.

Given the psychological challenges refugee workers face and their implications for refugee services, there is a notable absence of systematically tested intervention studies aimed at facilitating coping mechanisms for these individuals (Ebren et al., 2022). The current literature largely relies on guides prepared by civil society organizations. For

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instance, the "Health Ministry Staff Care and Self-Care Handbook" developed by the German International Cooperation (GIZ) explains concepts like STS, burnout, and stress, offering various coping methods such as breathing exercises and emotion regulation strategies (Alqudah, 2020). This guide aims to support refugee workers in managing these challenges effectively.

People In Aid and Interhealth organizations conducted a study in 2009 focusing on international civil society organizations, revealing that 55% of these organizations did not provide any personnel support systems. For example, a study involving 299 refugee workers in Iraq showed that only 38% of participants received supervision support (Eriksson, 2013).

While steps have been taken to improve in this area, there still lacks a developed and proven effective intervention program. Literature also includes studies examining the relationship between psychological and physical health among refugee workers. Rizkalla and Segal's (2019) study demonstrated how the number of refugees served and commitment to the employing civil society organization affect physical health. Similarly, Brooks' (2022) study highlighted the relationship between perceived support in the work environment and symptoms of STS and depression.

All these findings underscore the critical importance of improving working conditions for refugee workers, alongside intervention efforts aimed at addressing psychological challenges.

C. The Effects of Immigrant Workers on the Economy and the Labor Market

If we consider the issue through the lens of Syrian refugees under temporary protection; the large number of Syrians of working age underscores the importance of their participation in the workforce for integrating into the socioeconomic structure. The ability of Syrian immigrants and their families to sustain their lives and improve their welfare depends largely on their participation in the labor market. Due to the lack of legal permission to work and formal income sources in Turkey, they are often compelled to work under harsh conditions, especially in sectors like agriculture and construction (FairWear Foundation, 2016).

The participation of Syrian immigrants in the labor market can enhance the production of significant services in the country's economic infrastructure. For instance, they can contribute to the procurement of necessary tools and equipment for agricultural production and utilize idle agricultural capacity (Koç et al., 2015: 90). Syrian entrepreneurs are engaged in a wide range of sectors such as restaurants, real estate, construction, trade, textiles, travel, transportation, and food, often informally. Establishing businesses by Syrian migrants holds potential for both production and employment creation. One of the most significant contributions of migrant entrepreneurship is its role in addressing unemployment issues among other migrant groups (Afewerki, 2015: 16). Migrant business owners can create employment

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opportunities for both the local population and other migrants (Vinogradov and Isaksen, 2008: 6).

The effects of Syrian immigrants on Turkey's socio-economic structure can have both positive and negative consequences. First of all, the fact that Syrian immigrants are often employed below the minimum wage and find work in poor working conditions can lead to an increase in poverty and even the use of negative coping mechanisms such as child labor (International Rescue Committee, 2016). Research shows that the jobs that immigrants find through their own networks often include heavy and irregular payments and poor working conditions (Kaya and Kırac, 2016: 20).

The participation of Syrian immigrants in the labor market may, on the one hand, lead to an increase in unemployment rates and a worsening of the working conditions of the local workforce (Kaygısız, 2017: 9). Employing Syrian workers at lower costs may create wage pressure on the local workforce and lead to an increase in unregistered employment. According to the study of Akgündüz et al. (2015: 3), it was stated that inflation increased with the entry of immigrants into Turkey and house and food prices in the region increased, which may cause economic difficulties for the local people.

Del Carpio and Wagner's (2015) study revealed that the effects of immigrants on employment have negative consequences for domestic workers working in informal employment, part-time jobs and unskilled jobs. The reasons why Syrian immigrants are often employed in poor working conditions and in informal sectors are language barriers, low education levels, lack of validity of educational documents and economic needs (Özpinar et al., 2016: 2). This could increase unemployment rates of the domestic workforce and lead to worsening working conditions.

As a result, the participation of Syrian immigrants in the labor market in Turkey not only provides economic benefits, but also brings problems such as unemployment, social exclusion and unregistered employment. This situation emphasizes the importance of legal regulations' efforts to protect migrant workers' rights and prevent unregistered employment.

Unregistered work of Syrian immigrants in Turkey is a situation that can have both positive and negative effects. The positive effects of this situation include:

- **Employment Creation Effect:** Syrian immigrants working in unregistered jobs can contribute to employment creation in the economy. Using Syrian labor to meet the needs, especially in agriculture, construction, and service sectors, can help maintain balance in the labor market.
- **Income Effect:** The income earned by Syrian immigrants by working can contribute to the local economy. This revenue can bring economic vitality to local businesses and service providers.

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- **Effective Use of Resources:** Employment of Syrian immigrants can enable Turkey to use its workforce potential more effectively. It can contribute to the efficient use of resources, especially in seasonal work such as agriculture and the construction industry.
- **Increasing Competitiveness:** The use of Syrian workforce in some sectors can help businesses gain a competitive advantage by reducing their costs.

However, this situation also has negative effects, according to Yıldız's (2017: 44) study. These:

- **Decrease in Tax Revenues:** Unregistered employment may cause tax revenues to decrease. This situation may make financing public services difficult and negatively affect tax justice.
- **Distortion of Resource Distribution:** Informal economy can lead to unfair distribution of resources and questioning the accuracy of economic data.
- **Social Security Problems:** Failure of unregistered workers to contribute to the social security system may jeopardize the sustainability of the social security system.
- **Unfair Competition:** Unregistered work can create an unfair competitive environment in the labor market. The domestic workforce is likely to remain under pressure due to low wages and poor working conditions.
- **Child Labor and Exploitation:** In some cases, Syrian children working in unregistered jobs are also at risk of working and being exploited.

As a result, unregistered work of Syrian immigrants can provide economic advantages but also lead to serious social and economic problems. Therefore, it is important to develop effective policies and practices to reduce unregistered employment and integrate immigrants into the official labor market.

D. Difficulties Faced by Migrant Workers in Finding a Job and Starting a Business

The difficulties experienced by the Syrian immigrants we have taken as an example in finding a job and the solution suggestions for these difficulties are important for the integration of Syrian immigrants into the socio-economic structure of Turkey. Interviews with 17 Syrian workers and 13 employers living in İskenderun district of Hatay revealed that the majority had education below high school level and people with undergraduate and above education levels were in the minority (Gürsoy, 2019:10-19). The majority of immigrants in the labor market find jobs by benefiting from their professional experience. However, immigrants with high school education and university degrees have limited access to the labor market because these groups face certain permit and access difficulties."

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Immigrants frequently use social media platforms in their job search processes. In addition, job postings posted on windows and doors help immigrants find jobs as a traditional and informal method. A Syrian worker, a patisserie worker, expressed this situation as follows:

"Usually, people living in the same region inform each other when they are looking for a job. We announce that we are looking for a job on platforms such as Facebook and WhatsApp, and we find jobs through these channels. There are both job seekers and employers in Syrian immigrants' WhatsApp groups."

Another Syrian worker, a restaurant worker, similarly stated that Syrian immigrants found jobs through relationships among themselves and that official or non-governmental institutions did not help. He stated that intermediaries within social networks in the labor market, or people called "sergeants" as workers call them, helped them in the process of finding a job:

"We call the people who organize our work 'sergeant'. We do not have the chance to work in large enterprises. Usually, there is a 'sergeant' or 'teacher' at the head of each job. These people take responsibility for the workers and manage the recruitment process. Similar to the subcontractor system. "You may think, they hire us as subcontractors and employ us for daily wages. These people are usually Turks."

A Syrian employer who is a spotter similarly stated that he started the business through a friend. He stated that a Turkish friend manages all the processes (SGK registration, registration with the finance department, etc.):

"We established the business through a Turkish friend of ours. That friend carried out all the processes. Our Turkish friend handled all the procedures such as financial transactions and SSI registration. I can say that we work as partners in practice. He receives payment in return for the support he provides us. We go to him to run our business and we pay one payment at a time." We're doing it."

Another Syrian employer, who owns a store, stated that he does not use social media and is looking for a job individually. Later, they opened a store jointly with their friends and proceeded with the support of a financial advisor. However, he stated that they did not receive any help from any institution or organization in this process.

Similarly, another Syrian employer, who runs a patisserie, registered a business with financial consultancy support. He stated that all his permits and transactions were carried out by his financial advisors and that they did not receive official support from any institution or organization.

According to the research results, the ways Syrian immigrants find a job can be listed in the following order: primarily social networks (friends, relatives, environment, independent accountants, intermediaries), individual job search methods, traditional job

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finding methods (window and door advertisements) and effective use of social media. Study findings show that they generally do not receive support from civil or public institutions and that Syrian immigrants mostly find jobs through social networks. Demirağ and Kaya's study in 2016 emphasizes that Syrian women generally find jobs with the help of Syrian acquaintances and Turkish neighbors in their job search process. The research conducted by Erol and his team on the textile sector in 2017 revealed that half of Syrian immigrants found jobs by actively using horizontal social networks. These results are consistent with the findings of other studies.

It has been determined that immigrants face various difficulties in the labor market. These challenges include exclusion, language problems, workload, financial difficulties, lack of recognition of citizenship rights, difficulty finding employment, restrictions on free travel and cultural incompatibilities. At the Problems Facing Syrian Workers, Employers and Entrepreneurs in the Labor Market and Solution Suggestions Workshop organized by ILO (ILO) Turkey Office and Syrian Friendship Association in 2016, the main problems faced by immigrants were as follows:

- Need for Turkish language education
- Problems arising from the implementation of the legislation
- Dissemination of vocational training
- Child labor and problems in access to education
- The need for occupational mapping
- Diploma equivalence and qualification problem

These findings support the studies conducted. Solving immigrants' problems in the labor market can help increase their potential productivity. The problem of discrimination that immigrants are exposed to in business life and how these experiences are experienced is an important issue. The only female participant in the interview, a Syrian patisserie worker, stated that, according to her experience, she did not experience discrimination in the labor market. She stated that Turkish citizens generally treat them well.

“Working conditions in Syria were generally better for us, especially regarding working hours. In Syria, we usually worked until 16.00. However, most places in Turkey start early in the morning and continue until 20.00 in the evening. For this reason, we are experiencing difficulties in the adaptation process. We are having great difficulties in supporting our family. Many women come to Turkey with their widows and children. "This situation causes women to have a busy work schedule and to be unable to fully fulfill their household responsibilities."

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A Syrian worker working in a market stated that he experienced discrimination in the labor market. Syrian immigrants are employed to replace Turkish workers. This situation increases competition with the domestic workforce (Kaygısız, 2017: 8). Syrian immigrants who cannot negotiate wages and have to accept harsh working conditions can put the Turkish workforce at a disadvantage (Adar, 2018: 24). The worker describes the situation he experienced with the following words:

"We used to work with Turkish workers. Our working hours were longer and the salary we received was less. For example, when me and my brother-in-law were hired in a factory, where there were normally 6 workers, we started to do the work of only 6 people. While the Turkish workers were paid 2,500 TL, we were paid 800 TL."

The Syrian worker at the grocery store describes the difficulties he experienced with the following expressions:

"Everything is very expensive in Turkey. If my children did not work, it would be impossible for us to make ends meet. While working in the construction industry, I initially worked for 35 TL per day. Later, the daily wage increased to 50 TL, but business continuity could not be achieved. We were left with 15 thousand TL in a workplace. TOKİ worked for a year. "I worked at , but my employer did not pay us despite our contract."

The Syrian teacher stated that he received almost half the salaries of Turkish citizens despite doing the same job.

"The Syrian worker selling tobacco products particularly emphasized the workload problem. He stated that they were exposed to heavy working conditions and that their work was very tiring:

"While working in construction, we had to work as porters for the materials to be transported, and since there was no elevator, we had to carry cement and concrete especially on our backs. This caused great difficulties for me. I do not have any problems with behavior at work, but I had serious problems in terms of workload. There is no positive side to working here. Because the working hours are very long and the salary I receive is very low, my income was much better if I worked for 6 hours in my job in Syria."

Among the problems frequently seen in countries receiving immigrants, xenophobia and racism stand out. Problems such as exclusion, financial difficulties, harsh working conditions and discrimination are also commonly encountered (Öztürk and Çoltu, 2017: 192). A Syrian worker working in an auto-spare parts store stated that they were excluded by local workers and had a negative attitude towards immigrants:

"While I was looking for a job, Turkish workers said to me: 'Why are you working for such a low wage, we are working for this wage?' 'You are playing with our bread.' "We are trying to survive here with limited resources and we have to feed ourselves. We

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have difficulties in communicating with people... For example, if I am sick, I definitely have to come to work. However, it is okay if a Turkish worker does not come."

A Syrian worker working in a furniture store stated that he experienced discrimination and exclusion during the process of finding a job in the labor market. He stated that he encountered great difficulties in the job search process and had to wait for a while, and that some employers did not prefer him because he was Syrian. He stated that even after finding a job under difficult conditions, he could only earn enough money to support himself.

The Syrian employer, who owns a patisserie, stated that the biggest difficulties he experienced were the language problem and not having citizenship rights. He stated that having citizenship rights can bring success in different sectors. He emphasized that he could not benefit from opportunities such as taking out loans and receiving commercial support because he did not have citizenship rights. He also stated that he could only move where he was with a temporary ID, and that he could expand his business to different provinces if he had the opportunity to move freely.

As a result, let's summarize the main problems that Syrian immigrants face in the labor market in Turkey:

- Discrimination and exclusion problem (wage level, working hours and job for its content)
- Financial problems and difficulties
- Problems regarding workload and working conditions
- Difficulties in finding a job
- Temporary work
- Working in jobs outside of your competence
- Perceptions of the local workforce towards the employment of immigrants
- Difficulties with work permits
- Not recognizing the right to citizenship

Identifying the problems faced by immigrants can form an important basis for developing solutions for the integration of immigrants into the workforce in the future. Among the problems commonly seen in countries receiving immigrants, xenophobia and racism stand out. In addition, problems such as exclusion, economic difficulties, harsh working conditions and discrimination also arise (Öztürk and Çoltu, 2017: 192).

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Immigrants face difficulties such as discrimination, racism, exclusion, unregistered work and poverty, and these situations form the basis of the social problems faced by immigrants (Küçükşen, 2017: 2402). Research divides the problems faced by immigrants into categories such as discrimination-exclusion, economic difficulties, harsh working conditions, difficulties in finding and settling into a job, temporary jobs, working in unqualified jobs, relations with the local workforce, illegal work, failure to obtain citizenship rights, and cultural differences.

According to the results of the research, the majority of Syrian immigrants stated that they were satisfied with working or finding a job in Turkey, but they also expressed the cost of living as a difficulty. Even though working immigrants experienced some problems with their bosses or colleagues from time to time, they generally expressed their satisfaction. One of the issues that immigrants emphasize most is the safe environment of the country.

CONCLUSION

The psychological and economic dynamics of migrant workers play a critical role in shaping the modern labor market and societies. The issues of low wages, unemployment and integration discussed in this article have significant impacts on both the individual well-being and general economic and social cohesion of migrant workers.

Migrant workers often work in low-paid jobs, leading to economic insecurity and income inequality. These economic difficulties cause migrant workers to have difficulty meeting their basic needs, their quality of life decreases, and they live under constant financial stress. Economic uncertainty and insecurity have profound effects not only economically but also psychologically. Low income levels can negatively affect the self-worth and self-confidence of migrant workers, which can lead to serious deterioration in mental health in the long term.

Unemployment is one of the biggest problems faced by migrant workers. High unemployment rate not only increases the economic insecurity of migrant workers, but also negatively affects psychological health. During periods of unemployment, migrant workers experience intense stress and anxiety; This increases the risk of developing depression and other mental health problems. Inability to find employment can lead to social isolation and weakening of social cohesion. This makes it difficult for migrant workers to integrate into society and causes them to feel excluded.

The integration of migrant workers into their new societies is of critical importance for both economic and psychological health. The integration process requires migrant workers to learn the local language, access employment and professional development opportunities, and build social networks. Difficulties experienced in this process can increase the stress and anxiety levels of migrant workers. Failure to integrate successfully can cause migrant workers to feel excluded both at work and in social life. This negatively affects their psychological health and limits their contribution to society.

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Businesses and policy makers have important duties to improve the economic and psychological health of migrant workers. Businesses can contribute to this process by improving the working conditions of migrant workers, adopting fair wage policies and inclusive employment practices. Offering language training and professional development programs, ensuring psychological safety in the workplace, and increasing cultural sensitivity can facilitate the integration of migrant workers. Policy makers, on the other hand, should improve the economic and social conditions of migrant workers by developing legal regulations and social programs that protect and support their rights. Increasing access to healthcare, providing psychological counseling services, and strengthening social support networks are important steps in improving the overall well-being of migrant workers.

Findings from the literature show that refugee employees experience a variety of psychological difficulties such as Workplace Trauma (IT), Appraisal Trauma (DT), depression, anxiety, sleep disorders and burnout. These psychological difficulties lead to unethical behavior of aid workers and a decrease in the quality of services provided, resulting in workforce loss. However, despite existing findings, there is no proven effective psychological support intervention program for refugee employees yet.

As the number of refugees increases around the world, the importance of providing psychological support to refugee employees and improving their working conditions in order to create a sustainable aid system is increasing day by day.

As a result, low wages, unemployment and the difficulties migrant workers face in the integration process create profound effects both economically and psychologically. Solving these problems requires comprehensive and multidimensional approaches. It is critical for the success of this process that businesses and policy makers work in cooperation to improve the working conditions of migrant workers, protect their rights and provide psychological support. In this way, migrant workers can contribute to society as healthier, happier and more productive individuals, and the general welfare of societies increases. Policies and practices aimed at improving the welfare of migrant workers will benefit not only individuals but also the entire society.

RESTRICTION

Since national and international resources and scientific research are sufficient, no restrictions are stated on the subject.

NOTIFICATIONS

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external consultants.

Conflict of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest with this article.

Financial Support: The author reports no use of financial support with this article.

ETHICAL STATEMENT

Current Science is a nationally based scientific journal that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, respect for the findings and creations of others, and works to achieve this. The criteria of the Declaration of Helsinki were taken into account.

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